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“THE PSYCHOLINGUISTICS OF LANGUAGE LEARNING: INSIGHTS FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING”

As a language teacher, it has been my belief that what language is or what being proficient in a language means affects what you teach and how you teach it. I also take into consideration the idea that the emphasis of language teaching and learning must lay on the deep understanding of the learners' language learning process; hence, needs analysis is addressed in such a case. Knowing the needs of the learners, I am expected to give appropriate classroom activities that encourage them to engage in the pragmatic, authentic, and functional use of language for meaningful purposes. I honestly think I was so concerned about my views of language (e.g., language as rule-governed, language as meaning-based, and language as socially constructed) that I missed the towering importance of how students learn and the roles that enable them to learn in the classroom to some extent but not until I read about Psycholinguistics. Studying how word meaning, sentence meaning, and discourse meaning are computed and represented in the mind has given me very remarkable and valuable insights into the merging worlds of linguistics and psychology that I thought at first was never even possible.

The crux of studying Psycholinguistics circles significantly around the three investigated primary language processes and language knowledge such as language comprehension, language production, and language acquisition: specifically, it provides an exhaustive discussions on how our students produce and recognize speech, how they perceive words, letters, and sentences, how they can improve texts to make them easier to understand, how they learn and recall information from texts, and how the brain functions to process language, just to mention a few. It is always noteworthy to note that the crucial fact for understanding the place of language in human cognition is its diversity.

Another concept that has given needed insights to my field is that of Chomsky. It was the time of a radical and fundamental change when Chomsky criticized and published an influential critique on the shortcomings of the behaviorist approach of researchers such as B.F. Skinner who believed that any behavior whether linguistic or not can be taught through the complex relationship between the stimulus and response. Skinner's idea, obviously, does not run parallel to Chomsky's theory where he postulates that the human

mind is not a “black box”. He theorized the LAD (Language Acquisition Device), which according to him is an instinctive mental capacity which enables an infant to acquire and produce language. In other words, Chomsky firmly believes that humans are born with the instinct or “innate facility” for acquiring language. Bearing the name of language acquisition, Chomsky’s theory asserts that humans have an innate knowledge of the basic grammatical structure common to all human languages that gives clear contrast to the principle of behaviorist theory where it ascertains that infants learn oral language from other human role models through a process involving imitation, rewards, and practice.

In teaching, I realized that I was so much concerned about enhancing my students’ communicative competence that I may have raised my standard too high to reach without even considering or understanding their individual differences as they struggle meeting the bar. As that being said, I admit that I failed to use some appropriate teaching styles from the full gamut of teaching strategies that will suit their needs and their learning styles at their most appropriate pace. I failed to examine how my students even begin to understand or develop the ability to communicate. In short, I was too ambitious that I overlooked the fact that how students acquire the language or how the human mind develops, perceives, and produces both spoken and written communication will always be greatly influenced by some positive and/or negative factors aside from their unique social and cultural backgrounds or beliefs.

I have understood well from my readings that the complexity of psycholinguistics on how the process of teaching and learning are carried out plays a major role in the development of the teaching and learning English process. It is always a must for all teachers, especially English teachers, to know how language learning takes place in every student’s mind. Knowing this, the teacher may know and understand better how their students learn and acquire the language as expected of them.

It is, therefore, imperative to know the learning theories of Psycholinguistics for the teachers to continuously assess how students learn and at the same time to assess how we, teachers, can teach a language effectively. I clearly see the holistic role psycholinguistics has played in the understanding of how people learn languages at different stages of life. In other words, identifying students’ learning challenges where English is inherently difficult is deemed necessary to facilitate change and to spot the level of competence of the students according to the dimensions—form, meaning, or use of the language—it addresses and/or any other pertinent issues may arise about the way learning occurs.